

43 1. Introduction

44 Protein solubility over time is a critical factor across diverse research areas, including
45 biopharmaceutical formulation, industrial enzyme use, liquid–liquid phase separation, and
46 protein misfolding diseases[1–4]. Thermal stability studies are commonly used to evaluate
47 protein behaviour, but they often rely on phenomenological descriptions of melting profiles
48 rather than quantitative models. A predictive understanding of aggregation—particularly under
49 nonequilibrium conditions—requires experimental systems where unfolding and aggregation
50 can be interrogated independently, supported by kinetic modelling that captures how solubility
51 changes over time.

52 In this study, we focus on recombinant immunoglobulin light chains (LCs) derived from a
53 multiple myeloma patient[5] as a model for investigating sequence-dependent protein
54 aggregation and long-term solubility. Immunoglobulins (IgGs) are heteromeric proteins
55 essential to humoral immunity, composed of heavy and light chains joined by disulfide bonds
56 and shaped by post-translational modifications[6]. In healthy physiology, the biosynthesis and
57 assembly of IgGs are tightly controlled within plasma B-cells. However, dysregulation can
58 result in pathological overproduction of free light chains, particularly in conditions such as
59 multiple myeloma and amyloid light-chain (AL) amyloidosis.

60 In plasma cell dyscrasias, clonal B-cell expansion leads to excessive secretion of monoclonal
61 free LCs[7]. Depending on their intrinsic sequence properties and solution conditions, free LCs
62 may exhibit diverse aggregation behaviours, ranging from soluble species to higher-order
63 assemblies. Despite extensive biochemical characterisation of patient-derived LCs, the
64 mechanistic basis of why highly similar sequences behave so differently remains poorly
65 understood, largely because *in vivo* environments introduce additional complexity that masks
66 residue-specific effects.

67 To address this, we employ recombinant light chains expressed *in vitro*, enabling a systematic
68 investigation of sequence-dependent aggregation, the role of specific mutations, and the
69 structural features that contribute to misfolding. By combining solubility assays with rational
70 mutagenesis and kinetic modelling, we aim to dissect the determinants of light chain
71 aggregation quantitatively. This approach allows direct comparison of unfolding and
72 aggregation behaviours across variants under fully controlled conditions—going beyond our
73 earlier work, which examined global kinetic relationships but did not resolve the contributions
74 of individual residues. To date, no study has examined how minimal sequence changes in the
75 IGLV2 family—one of the most clinically relevant LC families—shape both conformational
76 stability and aggregation behaviour. Prior work focused primarily on IGLV6 light chains, which
77 differ substantially in sequence, germline origin, and aggregation hotspots. Here, we identify
78 and mechanistically dissect a previously unrecognised aggregation-prone segment in CDR1
79 of an IGLV2 light chain, demonstrate how mutations at positions 33 and 34 modulate both
80 unfolding energetics and supramolecular interactions, and provide experimental evidence that
81 Tyr34 stabilises higher-order assemblies through aromatic interactions. This work establishes
82 a quantitative link between local sequence variation in CDR1, non-cooperative unfolding
83 behaviour, and enhanced aggregation propensity under defined experimental conditions,
84 extending mechanistic insight beyond our earlier kinetic analyses.

85

86 2. Results

87 *Significant difference in the aggregation potential of sequentially-similar LCs*

88 Our previous studies focused on the kinetic modelling of the aggregation mechanism[8] and
89 establishing the aggregation model after disrupting stabilising disulfide bonds[9] of the lambda
90 light chain from the IGLV6 gene family. Here, we extend this framework to the IGLV2 gene
91 family and focus on identifying sequence determinants that modulate unfolding-coupled
92 aggregation under controlled *in vitro* conditions. We chose sequentially similar light chains that
93 differ in only 16 amino acids but show significantly different aggregation properties. The
94 sequences of both proteins were derived from the clinical dataset[5] and prepared by a
95 bacterial expression system. Light chain H9 (IGLV2-8 germline gene), previously reported in
96 association with cardiac AL amyloidosis, showed high colloidal stability *in vitro*, and even after
97 heating to high temperatures (under the temperature of transition) did not create naked-eye
98 visible sediments (Figure 1a). In contrast, the M10 light chain (IGLV2-14 germline gene),
99 derived from a multiple myeloma patient, exhibited pronounced colloidal instability and readily
100 formed visible aggregates upon heating (Figure 1a). After sequence alignment of both LCs,
101 differences of 16 amino acid positions in the variable domain were observed (Figure 1b). To
102 identify aggregation-prone regions of sequences, we provided bioinformatic analysis using the
103 TANGO software[10], which uses physicochemical principles for the calculation of the
104 Boltzmann distribution of secondary states of protein sequence, and the basic mechanism of
105 protein aggregation assumes the creation of intermolecular β -sheets.

106

107 **Figure 1:** (a) Solubility of light chains after heating the protein solution to 80 °C for 10 minutes – huge
 108 aggregate sediments of unstable M10 (left) and any visible aggregates of H9 (right). (b) Sequence
 109 alignment of M10 and H9, the differences in the amino acid sequence are highlighted in red. (c)
 110 Dependence of the position of amino acids on the tendency to aggregation calculated by the Tango
 111 algorithm. The red line represents the Tango score for M10 light chain, and the blue line represents the
 112 H9 LC. (d) The design of a new stable M10 light chain with two mutations in the CDR1 region, Ser33 to
 113 Asp (green sphere in 3D structure) and Tyr34 to Ser (blue sphere in 3D structure), determined by the
 114 Tango algorithm. PDB structure 5M6A was used as a reference for all figures.

115 In both cases, the aggregation-prone analysis showed high aggregation scores in three
 116 regions - at the amino acid positions of 47- 55 (CDR2 region), 132 – 139 (constant domain),
 117 and 145 – 150 (constant domain). In the case of the light chain M10, unlike H9, there has been
 118 identified a fourth region with a high aggregation score, at position 33 – 38 (Figure 1c). After
 119 comparing amino acids with protein H9, this aggregation-prone region differs just in 2 amino
 120 acids at positions 33 and 34, which are part of the CDR1 region. For this reason, we designed
 121 a mutant version of the M10 light chain with a mutated serine to aspartic acid at 33 and tyrosine
 122 to serine at 34 positions – M10 S33D/Y34S (Figure 1d).

123

124 *Monitoring of irreversible thermal denaturation of LCs*

125 The aggregation process is closely linked to the unfolding of molecules, which precedes the
126 clustering of molecules. First, we asked whether the studied pathological LCs (H9, M10) with
127 different aggregation potential and the designed mutated M10 S33D/Y34S also differ in their
128 thermal conformational stability.

129 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to measure the heat endotherm associated
130 with the unfolding of LC. The DSC thermogram at a scanning rate of 1 K/min revealed a single,
131 cooperative peak for light chain H9 and M10 S33D/Y34S, but a slightly asymmetric
132 endothermic peak in the case of M10 wild-type (Figure 2). The M10 unfolds in a broad peak,
133 which reflects the complexity of its thermal denaturation process, probably due to the creation
134 of intermediate forms and protein-protein interactions leading to formatted aggregates.
135 Reheating of the LC-cooled samples shows no detectable endotherm, suggesting that the
136 thermal unfolding process is irreversible. We investigated the thermal transitions of LC across
137 a concentration range of 10–40 μM . Within this concentration range, the melting temperatures
138 remain relatively stable (Table SI1), with only minimal changes observed in the overall shape
139 of the transition. Additionally, we explored scan rate dependence in the range of 0.5 – 2 K/min
140 to understand how the unfolding process varies with different heating rates. DSC thermograms
141 obtained at various scan rates (0.5 K/min – 2 K/min) reveal that the scan rate affects both the
142 position and shape of the unfolding LCs peaks. At higher scans, the unfolding peak tends to
143 shift to slightly higher temperatures.

144

145 **Figure 2:** (a) Concentration dependence of thermal transition curves (heating rate 1 K/min, 10 mM PBS
146 pH 7.4) - 10 μM (red), 20 μM (black) and 40 μM (blue). (b) Scan rate dependence of thermal transition
147 curves (10 μM LCs, 10 mM PBS pH7.4) of H9, M10_{WT} and M10 S33D/Y34S LCs – 0.5 K/min (black),

148 1.0 K/min (red), 1.5 K/min (blue), 2.0 K/min (green), points represents experimental data and solid line
149 represents fit, the black dashed line represents second scan after cooling sample.

150 The broadened and slightly asymmetric transition observed for M10WT indicates that its
151 unfolding is less cooperative than that of H9 or M10 S33D/Y34S. Such non-cooperative
152 behaviour suggests that M10 populates multiple partially unfolded species rather than a single
153 dominant unfolded state. These intermediates are expected to differ in the exposure of
154 aggregation-prone regions, which may contribute to the enhanced aggregation propensity of
155 M10 observed at elevated temperatures.

156 DSC measurements revealed that thermal unfolding of all three light chains proceeds
157 irreversibly and exhibits a clear dependence on scan rate, consistent with a kinetically
158 governed denaturation process. H9 and the M10 S33D/Y34S mutant display a single, well-
159 defined cooperative transition. In contrast, M10WT exhibits a broadened and slightly
160 asymmetric endotherm, indicating reduced cooperativity and the population of partially
161 unfolded intermediates.

162 To allow quantitative comparison across variants, all datasets were analysed using the same
163 two-state irreversible model; for M10_{WT}, this model does not represent a detailed mechanistic
164 description of the unfolding pathway. Instead, it is employed here as a phenomenological
165 approximation that enables quantitative comparison of apparent kinetic parameters across LC
166 variants under identical experimental conditions:

168 where k_{unf} is a first-order irreversible unfolding rate constant, which describes the irreversible
169 transformation of the native LC to the unfolded state. DSC data were fitted to this model by
170 using numerical integration in accordance with previous studies[11–13]. The results yielded a
171 characteristic temperature of transition (T_m) of ca. 53 °C for all three light chains. The solid
172 lines in Figure 2 represent the best fit of the two-state irreversible model to the experimental
173 DSC thermograms over the temperature range 40–65 °C. This visual agreement demonstrates
174 that the model provides a reasonable phenomenological description of the kinetically controlled
175 unfolding, and the extracted apparent activation energies (E_a) should be interpreted as overall
176 kinetic parameters rather than precise microscopic values. Comparable high apparent E_a
177 values have been reported for mutant Fab fragments under irreversible DSC conditions[13].
178 The activation energy (E_a) and temperatures of transition T_m are summarised in Table S11. The
179 E_a values for non-aggregating H9 and M10 S33D/Y34S are significantly higher than for the
180 aggregation-prone M10 wild-type. This suggests that the mutation of serine to aspartic acid
181 and tyrosine to serine at 33 and 34 positions increases the kinetic stability of the protein
182 through enthalpic, not the entropic effect. It should be noted that the melting temperature (T_m)
183 and the activation energy derived from the kinetic analysis reflect different aspects of protein
184 stability. While T_m represents the equilibrium temperature at which folded and unfolded states
185 are equally populated and therefore reflects thermodynamic stability, the activation energy
186 describes the kinetic barrier associated with the unfolding transition. Consequently, proteins
187 may exhibit similar T_m values while differing substantially in their unfolding kinetics if mutations
188 primarily affect the height of the unfolding barrier rather than the relative free energies of the
189 folded and unfolded states.

190

191 *Colloidal stability of light chains*

192 As we showed, after the heating treatment of light chains, the cardiotoxic H9 LC did not report
193 any visible sign of aggregation, and the solution seemed transparent (Figure 1a). For this

194 reason, we studied all three proteins – H9, M10, and mutant M10 S33D/Y34S - at the
 195 microscopic scale (Figure 3a). After visualisation of heated proteins (30 minutes at 65 °C) with
 196 an optical light microscope, we identified several small clusters of aggregated cardiotoxic H9,
 197 a huge cluster of M10, and minuscule aggregates of mutant M10. The images were then
 198 processed in the ImageJ-FIJI software to quantify the cluster's size; the largest aggregate,
 199 with a size of $1066.4 \pm 106.8 \mu\text{m}^2$ created by M10; similarly, small aggregates were found in
 200 the sample of H9 ($11.6 \pm 4.8 \mu\text{m}^2$) and M10 S33D/Y34S ($6.8 \pm 2.6 \mu\text{m}^2$). Because optical
 201 microscopy primarily detects micron-scale clusters, complementary structural characterisation
 202 of aggregates was performed using atomic force microscopy (AFM), which enables
 203 visualization of amyloid-based assemblies at nanoscale resolution (Fig. 3a, Fig. SI5a-d). In
 204 addition, amyloid formation was monitored using Thioflavin T fluorescence assays (Fig. SI5e),
 205 where all analysed light chains exhibited increased fluorescence emission at 480 nm,
 206 consistent with the formation of β -sheet-rich aggregates.

207 The fact that all three LCs form clusters, albeit only of microscopic dimensions, allowed us to
 208 conduct a deeper analysis of colloidal stability, defined by the interaction of molecules with
 209 each other in solution, i.e., their tendency to associate.

211 **Figure 3:** (a) Microscope images (up) and AFM images (down) of LCs aggregates prepared by heating
212 10 μM protein at 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 minutes. (b) Temperature dependence of colloidal stability H9, M10_{WT},
213 M10 S33D/Y34S LCs – the amount of soluble form of protein after heating at 50 (blue), 60 (cyan), 70
214 (green), 80 (black) and 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (red), the initial concentration of soluble LCs was 20 μM in PBS buffer. (c)
215 Dependence of LCs colloidal stability on the initial concentration of protein – the amount of soluble LCs
216 for the initial 10 μM (red), 20 μM (black), 30 μM (green) and 40 μM (blue) after heating at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

217 We used the sedimentation assay to monitor the amount of the soluble form of the protein. The
218 concentration of LC in soluble form was determined by UV-Vis spectroscopy. The changes in
219 solubility with temperature are shown in Figure 3b. In all variants, the soluble fraction
220 decreased monoexponentially. At 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, most of the protein remained soluble after 60 minutes
221 (H9 – 91 %; M10_{WT} – 66 %; M10 S33DY34S – 85 %). At 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the differences became more
222 pronounced – M10_{WT} lost most of its soluble fraction (only 18 % remained soluble after 60
223 minutes), whereas H9 and M10 S33D/Y34S retained 85 %. At 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the soluble fractions
224 decreased for all variants (42 % remaining for both H9 and the double mutant), although M10_{WT}
225 remained markedly less stable. Complete rate constants are listed in the SI2 table.

226 Since aggregation is by definition a multimolecular reaction, one would expect such kinetics
227 to be dependent on protein concentration. Figure 3c shows the solubility of each LC at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
228 as a function of initial protein concentration (rate constants listed in SI2 table). M10_{WT} displayed
229 strong concentration dependence, consistent with an aggregation mechanism involving
230 association of multiple molecular species. In contrast, H9 showed only a weak concentration
231 dependence, suggesting that although its aggregation is inherently multimolecular, the rate-
232 limiting step is less sensitive to bulk concentration.

233

234 *Temperature-dependent unfolding and multimolecular aggregation*

235 As we showed by scan-rate dependence in the DSC experiment, the thermal denaturation of
236 LC is an irreversible process under kinetic control. After analysing with the two-state
237 irreversible model (equation 1), we obtain a first-order irreversible rate constant k_{unf} , describing
238 the irreversible transformation of the native LC to the unfolded state. The temperature
239 dependency of the unfolding rate constant follows the Arrhenius equation. Using well-
240 established numerical analysis[11,12,14], our DSC data can be fitted very well, and the
241 activation energy and T^* (the temperature at which the microscopic rate constant, k , is equal
242 to 1 min^{-1} , see Equation 3) can be obtained.

243 Based on the calculated parameters from the DSC experiments, an Arrhenius plot, $\ln k_{unf}$ vs.
244 $1/T$ was constructed and is shown in Figure 4a. From this plot, the calculated activation energy
245 for $N \rightarrow U$ process is 605 kJ/mol for H9; 290 kJ/mol for M10; and 560 kJ/mol for the M10
246 S33D/Y34S. Apparent rate constant obtained from the solubility assay, which monitors the rate
247 of the aggregation ($nU \rightarrow Un$), shows a smaller temperature dependence; the activation energy
248 for the aggregation of the unfolded LC is 67 kJ/mol for H9; 45 kJ/mol for M10; and 78 kJ/mol
249 for M10 S33D/Y34S (Figure 4a).

250 Together, these analyses demonstrate that irreversible LC unfolding is governed by a high
251 activation barrier, whereas subsequent aggregation of unfolded species exhibits markedly
252 weaker temperature dependence.

253 The extent to which aggregation kinetics depend on protein concentration provides insight into
254 whether intermolecular association contributes to the rate-limiting step. To estimate the
255 apparent reaction order, we analysed the dependence of observed reaction half-times on the
256 initial LC concentration. Reaction half-times and order of the reaction can be obtained using
257 the following equation[15]:

$$\log\tau_{1/2} = \text{const.} - (n - 1)\log[\text{protein}]_{t=0s} \quad (2)$$

259 where n is the reaction order, and *const.* is a reaction-specific constant. First, we analysed our
260 DSC data at different LC concentrations using a two-state irreversible model.

261 Although LCs exist as a mixture of monomeric and dimeric species[8,9], the unfolding half-
262 times derived from DSC measurements show no systematic dependence on protein
263 concentration. The slope of $\ln\tau_{1/2}$ versus $\ln[\text{LC}]$ is 0.24 ± 0.20 for H9; 0.13 ± 0.04 for M10; and
264 0.05 ± 0.04 for M10 S33D/Y34S, corresponding to first-order kinetics (Figure 4b). Hence,
265 during the LC thermal denaturation, monomer/dimer equilibrium does not play a significant
266 role. In opposite, the aggregation reaction shows a strong concentration dependence of $\tau_{1/2}$.
267 The slope of $\ln\tau_{1/2}$ versus $\ln[\text{LC}]$ is -0.74 ± 0.50 for H9; -2.31 ± 0.58 for M10; and -1.99 ± 0.80
268 for M10 S33D/Y34S, which corresponds to apparent second-order kinetics. One should note
269 that the $\tau_{1/2}$ is observed half-time and does not specify the nature of the kinetic species
270 associated with the rate-limiting step. In summary, the unfolding rate constant does not depend
271 on initial protein concentration, and the aggregation rate constant depends strongly and
272 supports the notion that the association of two critical molecular species is needed.

273

274 **Figure 4:** (a) Graphical representation of the Arrhenius temperature dependence of irreversible LCs
275 unfolding and aggregation. (b) Concentration dependence of aggregation reaction and conformational
276 stability. The N state represents the native form of the protein, the U state is the protein in its unfolded
277 form, and U_n represents insoluble fibrils or aggregates. N to U change data were obtained from DSC
278 measurements. Conversion of U to fibrils/aggregates was determined by analysis of soluble LC
279 fractions.

280

281 *Role of the disulfide bridges in the colloidal stability*

282 Studied light chains contain 5 cysteines in the structure, four of them are joined in the
 283 intramolecular disulfide bridges, whereas cysteine at position 215 can stay in free thiol form or
 284 can form an intermolecular disulfide bond. This bridge makes a covalent connection between
 285 monomers. Proteins are usually strongly stabilised by disulfide bonds; hence, we were
 286 interested in whether the colloidal stability can affect destabilisation by reduction (Figure 5). In
 287 the experiments, after mixing 2 mM TCEP (tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine), a thiol-reducing
 288 agent, with 10 μM LC, an aggregation reaction was observed by monitoring absorbance
 289 changes at wavelengths which do not interfere with protein absorbance, i.e. 340 nm. We used
 290 a high-throughput workflow consisting of 96-well plates and a plate reader with pre-defined
 291 shaking times and amplitudes for the assay, as previously[9].

292 Reduction-induced aggregation assays revealed a pronounced contrast between H9 and M10
 293 variants. Whereas H9 remained resistant to aggregation upon disulfide bond reduction,
 294 showing no measurable change in absorbance over time, M10 displayed rapid aggregation
 295 following a characteristic sigmoidal kinetic profile with a lag phase for ca. 750 seconds after
 296 that, the rapid increase in absorbance can be observed, followed by an absorbance plateau
 297 (Fig. 5). Mutation of serine to aspartic acid and tyrosine to serine led to stabilisation of the
 298 protein up to 10 μM .

299

300 **Figure 5:** Aggregation kinetics after disruption of disulfide bonds with 2 mM TCEP of (a)H9; (b) M10_{WT};
 301 and (c) M10 S33D/Y34S – 30 μM (black), 20 μM (purple), 15 μM (blue), 10 μM (green), 7.5 μM (yellow)
 302 and 5 μM (red).

303 Because protein aggregation naturally involves the association of many molecules, we asked
 304 whether a multi-molecular association is a rate-limiting step. If so, increasing protein
 305 concentration should accelerate the observed time-dependent aggregation. We measured the
 306 aggregation kinetics of all three proteins at different protein concentrations, from 5 - 30 μM
 307 (Fig. 5). For stable H9, even increasing the concentration to 30 μM did not lead to the observed
 308 change in absorbance at 340 nm. In the case of M10, the final absorbance value increases
 309 dramatically as protein concentration increases. The final values for absorbance at 340 nm are
 310 0.05, 0.12, and 0.19 for 10, 20 and 30 μM . In contrast to large changes in final absorbance
 311 values, the lag phase is slightly affected. At 10 μM LC, the lag phase is 830 s, at 20 μM is 790
 312 s and at 30 μM is also 750 s. For M10 S33D/Y34S protein, no significant changes in
 313 absorbance up to 10 μM were observed, the signal slightly increased up to 20 μM , and a
 314 dramatic shift occurred at 30 μM . The final values for absorbance at 340 nm are 0.01, 0.04,
 315 and 0.15 for 10, 20 and 30 μM . In contrast to wild-type M10, larger changes were observed in
 316 the lag phase. At 20 μM LC, the lag phase is 2345 s, and at 30 μM is 1650 s.

317

318 *Contribution of aspartic acid and tyrosine to aggregation*

319 The mutation of serine to aspartic acid at 33 and tyrosine to serine at 34 positions in M10 led
320 to the stabilisation of LC. Next, we were curious about the contribution of single amino acids
321 to the aggregation and solving the aggregation pathway. We designed two new proteins of
322 M10 with single amino acid mutation – M10 S33D and M10 Y34S. Unfortunately, we cannot
323 purify the protein M10 Y34S, as it was poorly expressed in *E. coli* and finally aggregated.

324 For characterisation of the conformational unfolding changes and tendency to aggregate
325 formation of M10 S33D, we used methods described above – DSC for conformation stability
326 and sedimentation assay for colloidal stability. The investigation of the thermal transitions
327 across a concentration range of 10–40 μM showed that the melting temperatures remain
328 relatively stable with only minimal changes observed in the overall shape of the transition
329 (Figure SI 1a). Similarly, as in previous proteins, the transition is dependent on the scan rate
330 within the range 0.5 – 2 K/min (Figure SI 1b).

331 The thermal denaturation of LC is both scan-rate dependent and irreversible, indicating that
332 the process is kinetically controlled, and the denaturation behaviour can be described using
333 the same two-state irreversible model, yielding an activation energy (E_a) of approximately 655
334 kJ/mol and a characteristic temperature of transition (T_m) of ca. 60 °C.

335 For the monitoring of aggregate sediment creation, we used the sedimentation assay and the
336 soluble form of protein was monitored by absorbance at 280 nm. The changes in the amount
337 of the soluble form of LCs with temperature and concentration dependence are shown in Figure
338 SI 1c,d. As in previous light chains, the amount of the soluble form decreases
339 monoexponentially with time constants $6.7 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $10.0 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and
340 $11.7 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the reactions at 50, 60, and 70 °C. The molecularity of the
341 aggregation reaction was determined by the concentration dependency of the sedimentation
342 assay. We investigated the decrease of the soluble form of LC at 60 °C with different
343 concentrations of the initial native form. The monoexponential decay of soluble form at 10 μM
344 has taken with a time constant of $1.7 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$; at 20 μM $11.7 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$; and
345 $21.7 \times 10^{-4} \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 40 μM . The evident concentration dependence of observed time
346 constants suggests that the transformation of the soluble form of M10 S33D into insoluble
347 aggregates is a multimolecular process.

348 As described above, we used numerical analysis for the analysis of data. Based on the
349 calculated parameters from the DSC experiments, an Arrhenius plot $\ln k_{unf}$ vs. $1/T$ was
350 constructed and is shown in Figure SI2a ($N \rightarrow U$). From this plot, the calculated activation
351 energy for unfolding is 660 kJ/mol. The apparent rate constant obtained from the solubility
352 assay, which monitors the rate of aggregation ($nU \rightarrow Un$), shows a smaller temperature
353 dependence; the activation energy for the aggregation of the unfolded LC is 53 kJ/mol.

354 The calculated half-times from DSC at different concentrations are independent of protein
355 concentration. The slope of $\ln \tau_{1/2}$ versus $\ln [\text{LC}]$ is 0.19 ± 0.22 , corresponding to first-order
356 kinetics (Figure SI2b). Hence, during the LC thermal denaturation, monomer/dimer equilibrium
357 does not play a significant role. In contrast, the aggregation reaction shows a strong
358 concentration dependence of $\tau_{1/2}$; the slope of $\ln \tau_{1/2}$ versus $\ln [\text{LC}]$ is -2.31 ± 0.50 ,
359 corresponding to apparent second-order kinetics.

360

361 Next, we were interested in the aggregation sensitivity of M10S33D after disruption of the
362 disulfide bonds (Figure SI 1e). After the addition of 2 mM TCEP, the changes in the absorbance
363 led to an increase of value in a sigmoidal manner to the final absorbance value at 340 nm,
364 0.06, 0.12, and 0.18 for 10, 20 and 30 μM . The lag phase is slightly affected. At 10 μM LC, the
365 lag phase is 1550 s, at 20 μM is 1420 s and at 30 μM is also 1420 s.

366 From the previous section, one can conclude that the mutation of serine to aspartic acid
 367 stabilises the protein and suppresses the aggregation; however, the effect is not so
 368 pronounced as in M10 S33D/Y34S. We were curious about the contribution of tyrosine to the
 369 aggregation in wild-type M10. As we mentioned, we were not able to purify mutant M10 Y34S,
 370 so we changed our approach and monitored changes in reduction aggregation kinetics in all
 371 three versions of M10 – wild-type (Ser33, Tyr34); single amino acid mutant (Asp33, Tyr34) and
 372 double amino acid mutant (Asp33, Ser34) after external addition of 1 mM tyrosine (Figure 6).
 373 In both proteins containing tyrosine at position 34 in the primary structure, wild-type M10 and
 374 M10 S33D, there was no difference between the kinetics with and without 1 mM tyrosine; the
 375 lag phase, slope of aggregation and final magnitude were the same. In the case of a mutant
 376 without tyrosine in the primary sequence, M10 S33D/Y34S, the shape of the curve differed.
 377 The previously described moderate aggregation was dramatically changed in the presence of
 378 1 mM tyrosine (Figure 6c, red line). The lag phase remained unchanged at 1550 s, but the final
 379 magnitude robustly increased to $A_{340} = 0.15$, comparable to M10 wild-type and M10 S33D.

380

381 **Figure 6:** 3D structures show amino acid variations in the CDR1 region, and aggregation kinetics after
 382 disulfide bonds disruption without (black lines) and with 1 mM tyrosine (red lines) of M10_{WT} (a), M10
 383 S33D (b), M10 S33D/Y34S (c).

384 In summary, the introduction of the negative charge in the CDR region by mutation of serine to
 385 aspartic acid does not alter the aggregation pathway – irreversible, strongly temperature-
 386 dependent LC unfolding is followed by multimolecular aggregation with significantly lower
 387 temperature dependence. The addition of external tyrosine does not affect the pathway of
 388 aggregation, whereas the kinetic parameter, lag phase, remains intact. These results are
 389 consistent with the involvement of aromatic interactions in stabilising intermolecular
 390 assemblies.

391

392 **3. Discussion**

393 *Minor sequence variations can dramatically alter protein stability and aggregation behaviour*

394 Unlike our previous work on IGLV6 light chains, the present study focuses on the clinically
395 relevant IGLV2 family and reveals an aggregation hotspot in CDR1 that has not been reported
396 previously. Although our earlier work demonstrated general kinetic features of LC unfolding
397 and aggregation, the current results provide new mechanistic insights by showing how two
398 natural substitutions (Ser33 and Tyr34) modulate unfolding cooperativity, kinetic stability, and
399 supramolecular assembly. This establishes a direct and previously uncharacterised
400 relationship between CDR1 sequence variation and aggregation behaviour in IGLV2 light
401 chains. Our study demonstrates that even minimal sequence variations between homologous
402 immunoglobulin light chains (LCs) can lead to significant differences in their aggregation
403 behaviour. Specifically, the M10 LC, differing from H9 by only 16 amino acids, exhibited
404 markedly higher aggregation propensity under thermal stress. This observation aligns with
405 previous research highlighting how subtle sequence differences can influence protein stability
406 and aggregation behaviour. Peterson et al. (2010)[16] revealed that a single point mutation in
407 the LC variable domain can promote amyloidogenicity by creating a promiscuous dimer
408 interface, facilitating aberrant self-association. Similarly, Marin-Argany et al. (2015)[17]
409 demonstrated that certain mutations can render LCs either too stable or too unstable to form
410 amyloid fibrils, emphasising the importance of a delicate balance in protein stability for amyloid
411 formation. Randles et al. (2009)[18] provided insights into how structural alterations within
412 native amyloidogenic LCs, induced by specific mutations, can destabilise the protein, leading
413 to increased aggregation propensity.

414 We were interested in how individual amino acids can contribute to aggregation propensity and
415 whether there is some trend. For this reason, we simulated the mutation of individual amino
416 acids at positions 33 or 34 of M10_{WT} and looked at the predicted TANGO score (Figure SI3). It
417 should be noted that sequence-based aggregation predictors such as TANGO identify short
418 sequence segments with intrinsic β -aggregation propensity but do not explicitly account for the
419 structural context of residues within the folded protein or for long-range stabilising interactions.
420 In multidomain proteins such as immunoglobulin light chains, the exposure of aggregation-
421 prone segments depends strongly on the stability of the native fold and on unfolding kinetics.
422 Therefore, in the present study TANGO analysis was used primarily as a guiding tool to identify
423 candidate regions for mutational analysis rather than as a quantitative predictor of aggregation
424 behaviour. The substitution of serine and tyrosine for hydrophobic amino acids (Ala, Ile, Leu,
425 Val) leads to a significantly high aggregation score. Baden et al. (2008)[19] highlighted that
426 mutations can cause local structural perturbations, exposing hydrophobic regions that promote
427 amyloidogenesis. Aromatic interactions of amino acids by π -stacking contribute to the
428 structural stabilisation of amyloid fibrils [20–22]. Also, our simulation with introduced aromatic
429 acids (Phe, Tyr, Trp) led to the high aggregation TANGO values.

430 To assess whether the identified aggregation-prone segment is unique to the analysed variants
431 or represents a broader feature of λ light chains, we additionally examined the CDR1 region of
432 representative human IGLV germline sequences using TANGO (Figure SI7). Several
433 sequences display moderate aggregation propensity within this segment, typically associated
434 with the presence of hydrophobic or aromatic residues such as valine, tyrosine or tryptophan.
435 Notably, the CDR1 sequence of the aggregation-prone M10 variant (YVWVY) exhibits the
436 highest predicted aggregation tendency among the analysed sequences. These observations
437 support the interpretation that the CDR1 region represents an aggregation-sensitive hotspot in
438 λ light chains, where relatively small sequence variations can strongly influence aggregation
439 propensity.

440 From a clinical aspect, after the alignment of light chain sequences, the hydrophobic leucine
441 was found at position 34 in M2, M8, and M9 light chain samples of patients with multiple

442 myeloma. The aromatic amino acids also play a significant role in the aggregation-critical
 443 location; the phenylalanine at position 34 was found in the light chain H7 of a 45-year-old
 444 patient with cardiac amyloidosis, whereas tyrosine at this position was found in multiple
 445 myeloma patients with LC codes M7, M10 and in LCs H6, H15 and H18 samples of patients
 446 with amyloidosis of LC with multiple organs involved (heart, kidney, peripheral nervous system,
 447 soft tissues)[5].

448 In our case, the additional aggregation-prone region identified in M10, absent in H9,
 449 corresponds to two substitutions within the CDR1 region. This suggests that these specific
 450 residues may play a pivotal role in modulating the LC's conformational dynamics, leading to
 451 increased aggregation. These findings reinforce the notion that even minor sequence
 452 variations, particularly in regions critical for maintaining structural integrity, can have substantial
 453 effects on protein aggregation behaviour.

454 To further examine the role of residues at positions 33 and 34 in modulating aggregation
 455 behaviour, we generated the reciprocal mutant of the H9 light chain (H9 D33S/S34Y),
 456 introducing the residues present in the aggregation-prone M10 variant. Analysis of the
 457 aggregation kinetics revealed a moderate increase in aggregation propensity compared with
 458 the wild-type H9 protein under identical experimental conditions (Supplementary Figure S18).
 459 Although the effect is less pronounced than in the M10 background, this result supports the
 460 interpretation that residues within the CDR1 region contribute to the modulation of aggregation
 461 behaviour in IGLV2 light chains.

462 Based on our findings, studied by robust assays, we suggest the model of the aggregation and
 463 anti-aggregation impression of individual amino acids in the critical aggregation-prone side
 464 (Figure 7).

465

466 **Figure 7:** An energy barrier leading to the unfolding of the native form and the formation of aggregates.
 467 Simplified LC reaction coordinate and activation energies for individual steps were obtained by DSC

468 measurements and colloidal stability analysis. The transformation of the native light chain to the unfolded
469 state is the rate-limiting unimolecular step requiring an activation energy of ~ 290 kJ/mol in M10_{WT} (a)
470 and ~ 560 kJ/mol in M10 S33D/Y34S (b). The formation of aggregates is a bimolecular step with an
471 activation energy of ~ 10 kJ/mol in M10_{WT} and ~ 70 kJ/mol in M10 S33D/Y34S. In M10_{WT}, the tyrosine
472 contributes to the stabilisation of intermolecular interactions and leads to the creation of huge sediments.
473 The mutation of the supramolecular stabilisation tyrosine in M10 S33D/Y34S, together with the
474 introduction of charge by mutation of Ser33 to Asp in the critical aggregation interface, stabilises the
475 molecule and suppresses the formation of sediments.

476 Although previous studies Oberti et al.[5] reported H9 LC to be less stable and more
477 dynamically disordered than M10; these findings are not inconsistent with our observation.
478 Protein rigidity and aggregation are related in a non-linear manner – both excessive flexibility
479 and excessive rigidity can promote aggregation through different mechanisms. A more rigid
480 LC, such as M10, may display high thermodynamic stability yet remain highly aggregation-
481 prone under stress conditions because reduced conformational adaptability can diminish
482 solubility and promote intermolecular association[23].

483 It should be noted that aggregation behaviour observed under controlled *in vitro* conditions
484 does not necessarily translate directly to amyloid deposition in patients. Clinical manifestation
485 of AL amyloidosis depends on multiple factors including light-chain concentration, proteolytic
486 processing, and interactions with the tissue environment. Therefore, the aggregation
487 propensity observed for the M10 variant in this study should be interpreted primarily as
488 reflecting intrinsic sequence-dependent properties of the LC rather than as direct evidence of
489 amyloid formation *in vivo*.

490

491 *Electrostatic repulsion protects against aggregation*

492 The introduction of charged residues can significantly influence the solubility and reduce the
493 aggregation propensity. In our study, the substitution of serine at position 33 with aspartic acid
494 (S33D) in M10 introduces a negative charge in the CDR1 region. This modification likely
495 enhances electrostatic repulsion between LC molecules, thereby reducing aggregation
496 propensity.

497 Similar strategies have been explored in antibody engineering: Lee et al. (2013)[24]
498 demonstrated that adding charged residues can disrupt hydrophobic contacts that initiate
499 aggregation, providing a rational design principle for improving antibody stability. Consistent
500 with this idea, mutations such as F101D in the VL–VL interface and F122D in the CL–CL
501 interface have been shown to weaken aggregation-prone contacts and decrease aggregation
502 propensity[25].

503 Importantly, position 33 lies immediately adjacent to the CDR1 aggregation-prone segment
504 predicted by TANGO. Residues flanking aggregation-prone regions frequently act as
505 gatekeepers—typically charged or proline residues—that inhibit β -aggregation by introducing
506 electrostatic or steric barriers. This gatekeeper principle is well established across amyloid-
507 forming proteins and has also been described for immunoglobulin light chains[26–28].
508 Although Ser33 is not a classical gatekeeper, its replacement with Asp introduces a negative
509 charge at this critical boundary, functionally mimicking a gatekeeper residue. Consistent with
510 this mechanism, the S33D mutation markedly reduces aggregation while leaving thermal
511 stability largely unchanged.

512 Together, these observations suggest that introducing negative charges at the edges of
513 aggregation-prone segments—such as CDR1—can effectively protect against aggregation.

514 This principle may be valuable in the rational design of therapeutic antibodies with improved
515 solubility and stability profiles.[24][25]

516

517 *Tyrosine residues influence supramolecular integrity*

518 Tyrosine residues play a critical role in modulating the supramolecular integrity of aggregates
519 formed by immunoglobulin light chains (LCs). In particular, our analysis reveals that
520 substitutions involving tyrosine residues influence aggregation kinetics and fibril stability. This
521 observation is in line with previous studies demonstrating that tyrosine contributes to the
522 stabilisation of dynamic intermolecular interactions in LC fibrils.

523 DiCostanzo et al. (2012) showed that tyrosine residues mediate fibril formation via π -stacking
524 and hydrogen bonding at the LC dimer interface, highlighting their structural and functional
525 relevance in fibril organisation[29]. This is corroborated by recent Cryo-EM structures of
526 amyloidogenic LC fibrils[30,31], such as those in PDB entries 8CPE and 6HUD, where Tyr34
527 plays a key role in supramolecular assembly. Specifically, Tyr34 engages in hydrogen bonding
528 with His33, Tyr34, and Val35 of an adjacent LC molecule, effectively stabilising the inter-subunit
529 interface within the fibril core. These interactions underscore the dual structural and functional
530 role of tyrosine residues in maintaining fibril morphology and promoting amyloid stability.

531 Taken together, these observations suggest that Tyr34 contributes to intermolecular
532 interactions involved in LC aggregation. The effects observed upon addition of free tyrosine
533 support the involvement of aromatic-mediated interactions; however, free tyrosine in solution
534 cannot fully reproduce the geometric constraints and packing interactions of a residue
535 embedded within the protein structure. Therefore, these results should be interpreted as being
536 consistent with aromatic contributions to aggregate stabilisation rather than as direct evidence
537 for specific π - π stacking interactions within the fibril interface. Targeting such residues may
538 offer a strategy for modulating LC aggregation and designing therapeutics against LC
539 amyloidosis.

540

541 **4. Conclusion**

542 This study highlights how subtle sequence variations in immunoglobulin light chains critically
543 shape their conformational stability and aggregation behaviour. We found that hydrophobic
544 and aromatic substitutions, particularly at Tyr34 within the CDR1 region, enhance aggregation
545 potential by stabilising supramolecular interactions, whereas the introduction of charged
546 residues, such as S33D, mitigates aggregation through electrostatic repulsion. Energetic
547 profiling revealed that these mutations markedly alter the barriers to unfolding and aggregation,
548 illustrating the fine balance between structural stability and aggregate formation. Importantly,
549 the recurrence of hydrophobic and aromatic residues at key positions in patient-derived
550 sequences underscores their pathogenic significance. Our findings not only provide
551 mechanistic insights into light chain amyloidosis but also suggest that rational incorporation of
552 charged residues may offer a promising strategy for developing aggregation-resistant
553 therapeutic antibodies.

554

555 **5. Materials and methods**

556 Two full-length λ immunoglobulin light chains, H9 and M10, were selected as model systems
557 for this study. H9 originated from a 59-year-old patient diagnosed with cardiac AL amyloidosis,

558 whereas M10 was derived from a 55-year-old patient with multiple myeloma without detectable
559 organ involvement. The sequences of H9, M10 and M10 variants (S33D/Y34S and S33D) were
560 synthesised by GeneScript. Genes were cloned into the pET-11a expression vector using NdeI
561 and BamHI restriction sites; all sequences are listed in the Supplementary Information.

562 **Protein expression and purification**

563 Expression plasmids encoding SUMO-fused light chains were transformed into *Escherichia*
564 *coli* Shuffle T7 cells. Cells were grown in LB medium supplemented with ampicillin (100 µg/mL)
565 at 37 °C until mid-log phase (OD600 = 0.6). The expression of proteins was induced using
566 isopropyl-β-D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) at a final concentration of 1 mM. Following 5 h
567 of induction at 37 °C, cells were collected by centrifugation (7,500 g, 10 min, 4 °C) and
568 resuspended in lysis buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0, 100 mM NaCl, 1 mM PMSF). Cell
569 disruption was achieved by sonication (Branson Sonifier 450; output control 5, duty cycle 60
570 %, 30 pulses with three repetitions) followed by clarification by centrifugation (15,000 g, 30
571 min, 4 °C). The supernatant was filtered (0.45 µm) and applied to a Ni-NTA HisTrap HP column
572 pre-equilibrated with buffer A (50 mM TRIS-HCl, 100 mM NaCl, 5 mM imidazole buffer, pH 8.0).
573 After washing with three column volumes of buffer A, bound proteins were eluted using buffer
574 B (50 mM TRIS-HCl, 100 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole buffer, pH 8.0). In the next step, the N-
575 terminal SUMO-tag was cleaved by incubation with Senp2 protease (His-tagged) for 4 hours,
576 loaded onto a nickel column, and eluted by buffer A. Final purification was performed by size-
577 exclusion chromatography using a Superdex 75 Increase 10/300 GL (GE Healthcare) column
578 equilibrated in 10 mM PBS pH 7.4, at a flow rate 0.5 ml/min. Protein concentration was
579 determined by UV absorbance at 280 nm using a Thermo Scientific NanoDrop One
580 spectrophotometer, with extinction coefficients calculated using ProtParam. SDS PAGE gels
581 from individual purification steps are shown in Figure S14.

582 **MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry**

583 Protein samples were mixed with α cyano 4 hydroxycinnamic acid MALDI matrix (HCCA;
584 Bruker Daltonics, Germany) and spotted onto the stainless steel MALDI target plate (Bruker
585 Daltonics, Germany). Spectra were acquired by UltrafleXtreme MALDI TOF/TOF mass
586 spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics Germany) using flexcontrol software in positive linear mode.
587 The mass range was set from 2000 to 30 000 m/z. Post processing of raw data was performed
588 with FlexAnalysis software (Bruker Daltonics).

589 **Differential Scanning Calorimetry**

590 DSC measurements were carried out using a VP-Capillary DSC instrument (Microcal Inc.,
591 Malvern Instruments Ltd.). Light chains were analysed at concentrations of 10, 20, and 40 µM
592 in PBS buffer (10 mM, pH 7.4), which was also used as a reference. Samples were heated
593 from 25 to 90 °C at a scan rate of 1 K/min with a filtering period 10 s. Scan-rate dependence
594 was assessed at 0.5; 1.0; 1.5, and 2.0 K/min with corresponding filter periods of 25; 10; 8, and
595 5 s at a constant protein concentration 10 µM. All experiments were performed in three repeats.
596 Thermograms were baseline-corrected by subtracting a sigmoidal function and normalised to
597 the molar concentration of the protein.

598 Temperature transitions obtained by DSC were analysed by equations for a kinetic two-state
599 irreversible model. The rate constants at a given temperature were obtained from the Arrhenius
600 equation:

$$601 \quad k = \exp \left[\frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T^*} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

602 where R is the gas constant ($R = 8.314 \text{ J/mol/K}$), T^* is the temperature at which the microscopic
603 rate constant k is equal to 1 min^{-1} , and E_a is the activation energy.

604 **Microscopy**

605 Protein aggregates were generated by incubating $10 \mu\text{M}$ LC solutions in PBS buffer (10 mM ,
606 $\text{pH } 7.4$) at $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min . Following incubation, $10 \mu\text{L}$ of each sample was deposited onto a
607 clean glass microscope slide and covered with a coverslip for imaging. Aggregates were
608 visualised using an optical microscope (Konus College Bio Microscope) equipped with a $40\times$
609 objective and a CMOS camera (Kern ODC 825, 5.1 MP). Images were acquired under identical
610 illumination and exposure settings for all samples to ensure comparability. For each protein
611 variant, at least $5\text{--}10$ independent fields of view were recorded from three independent sample
612 preparations. The obtained images were analysed using FIJI/ImageJ software (National
613 Institutes of Health, USA). Background subtraction was applied to improve aggregate contrast.
614 Aggregate areas were determined by threshold-based particle analysis, and the reported
615 values represent mean \pm standard deviation calculated from multiple aggregates detected
616 across the analysed fields.

617 **Atomic force microscopy**

618 To visualize aggregates of light chain (LC) proteins H9, M10, and the mutants M10 S33D and
619 M10 S33D/Y34S, protein samples ($10 \mu\text{M}$) were thermally treated at $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min prior to
620 AFM analysis. For imaging, $10 \mu\text{L}$ aliquots of the thermally treated samples were deposited
621 onto freshly cleaved V1 mica discs (Ted Pella, Inc., Redding, CA, USA), allowed to adsorb for
622 $5\text{--}10 \text{ min}$ at room temperature ($20 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), gently washed with ultrapure water ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$),
623 and dried under a soft stream of nitrogen. AFM images were acquired in tapping mode using
624 a Veeco di Innova scanning probe microscope (Bruker AXS Inc., Madison, WI, USA) with an
625 NCHV cantilever (force constant 42 N/m , nominal resonance frequency 320 kHz , tip radius
626 10 nm), at a scan rate of $0.70\text{--}0.75 \text{ kHz}$ and 1024×1024 pixel resolution. The images are
627 presented as acquired and exported using NanoScope Analysis 1.20 (Bruker AXS Inc.,
628 Madison, WI, USA) without additional processing.

629 **Thioflavin T fluorescence assay**

630 To verify the formation of cross- β -rich structures characteristic of amyloid-like aggregates,
631 thermally treated LC proteins (H9, M10, M10 S33D, and M10 S33D/Y34S; $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 30 min) were
632 incubated with Thioflavin T (ThT, T3516, Sigma-Aldrich) at a protein-to-dye ratio of $1:3$, yielding
633 final concentrations of $10 \mu\text{M}$ protein and $30 \mu\text{M}$ ThT. Samples were incubated for 1 h in the
634 dark at $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and fluorescence emission was measured in a 96-well microplate using a
635 Synergy MX spectrofluorometer (BioTek) with excitation at 440 nm and emission at 485 nm ;
636 excitation and emission slits were 9.0 nm , and the top probe vertical offset was 6 nm .

637 **Sedimentation aggregation assay**

638 Colloidal stability was assessed by monitoring temperature-induced sedimentation of LCs.
639 Protein aliquots were incubated at temperatures between 50 and $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; at defined time points,
640 reactions were quenched by transferring samples onto ice. Samples were centrifuged ($20\,000$
641 g , 15 min , 4°C), and the concentration of the soluble LC was determined by absorbance at 280
642 nm . To evaluate the temperature dependence of LC solubility, experiments were performed at
643 a fixed protein concentration of $20 \mu\text{M}$ in PBS buffer. Concentration-dependent measurements
644 were carried out at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using LC concentrations between 10 and $40 \mu\text{M}$. All experiments
645 were performed in three technical replicates. Rate constants were obtained by fitting the time-
646 dependent decrease in soluble protein to an exponential decay function:

$$647 \quad S = S_0 + A \times e^{(-kt)} \quad (4)$$

648 where S represents absorbance at 280 nm, S_0 is the initial absorbance, A is the pre-exponential
649 factor, k is the apparent rate constant, and t denotes time.

650 **Reduction-aggregation assay**

651 Aggregation kinetics initiated by disulfide bond reduction were monitored using a Agilent
652 BioTek Synergy HTX microplate reader controlled by Gen5 software. Measurements were
653 carried out at 50 °C with absorbance recorded at 340 nm. Prior to each readout, samples were
654 mixed by orbital shaking for 10 s at 1096 cpm. All experiments were performed in three
655 technical replicates. For concentration-dependent measurements, tris(2-
656 carboxyethyl)phosphine (TCEP) was added to a final concentration of 2 mM, while LC
657 concentrations ranged from 5 to 30 μ M.

658 To assess the effect of free tyrosine on aggregation, the same experimental setup was used
659 with the addition of 1 mM tyrosine to samples containing 20 μ M LC.

660

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670

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